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CLINICAL AND NEUROLOGICAL FEATURES OF PROFESSIONAL MYOFASCIAL PAIN SYNDROME OF THE NECK

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Abstract. This article analyses the clinical forms of myofascial pain syndrome, the location of trigger points, the frequency of neurological deficits, and psycho-emotional indicators in office employees, manufacturing employees, and medical staff. It has been shown that manufacturing employees demonstrate the most pronounced manifestations of pain, neurological deficits, while office employees are characterised mainly by static loads and moderate symptoms. The results highlight the need for professionally-oriented diagnostics, an individualised approach to treatment, and comprehensive rehabilitation to reduce the frequency of relapses and maintain working capacity.

Keywords: myofascial pain syndrome, neck, trigger points, neurological deficit, occupational risk.

Relevance. Myofascial pain syndrome (MPS) of the neck is one of the leading causes of temporary and permanent disability in people of working age, significantly affecting their quality of life and professional activity [1–3]. The nature of professional activity significantly influences the formation of trigger points, the severity of pain syndrome, and functional disorders [4]. Given the limited effectiveness of standard treatment methods and the high frequency of relapses, especially in individuals with long-term work experience, the current task is to develop comprehensive, professionally oriented programmes for diagnosis, treatment and rehabilitation, including ergonomic correction, physical therapy and psychological correction [5, 6]. The implementation of such approaches makes it possible to reduce the severity of pain, decrease the frequency of relapses, and maintain the working capacity of patients from various professional groups.

The aim of the research is to study the clinical and neurological features of myofascial pain syndrome of the neck, as well as functional and muscular disorders.

Materials and methods. We conducted a comprehensive examination of 180 patients aged 40–60 years. The clinical and functional examination included inspection and palpation of the muscles to identify active trigger points in order to determine the location and nature of the lesion. The neurological examination included assessment of sensory disturbances, muscle strength, and identification of autonomic symptoms.

Statistical data processing included descriptive statistics (mean \pm standard error, $M \pm m$), comparative analysis between groups using Student's t-test for quantitative indicators and χ^2 for categorical data. The level of statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$, which allowed for the reliable identification of differences and dependencies between indicators in different professional groups.

Research results. When distributing the clinical signs of myofascial pain syndrome among office employees, manufacturing employees, and medical staff, it was found that trigger points were most often detected on the back of the neck in all groups, with the percentage of patients with this localisation being higher among manufacturing employees and medical staff (76.4% and 73.3%) compared to office workers (58.5%). The upper part of the trapezius muscle is also a common source of pain, especially among industrial workers (69.1%), reflecting the impact of physical exertion and heavy lifting on the shoulder girdle. The subscapular region is affected less frequently, but its prevalence is higher among manufacturing employees (45.5%) and medical personnel (30.0%) than among office employees (18.5%), which is associated with mechanical overload of the shoulder girdle during physical activity. Bilateral manifestations of MFPS predominate in all professional groups (63.1–67.3%), indicating symmetrical damage to the muscles of the cervical-brachial region. Unilateral processes were less common (32.7–36.9%) (fig.1).

Figure 1. Structure of clinical forms of MFPS by occupational groups

Cervicalgia was observed in most patients in all groups (71.7–85.5%), confirming the close relationship between MFPS and pain syndrome in the cervical spine. Cervicobrachialgia, reflecting pain radiating to the arm and shoulder, was more common among manufacturing employees (63.6%), which may be associated with intense physical exertion and repetitive movements. This indicator was lower among office employees (35.4%) and medical staff (46.7%).

Figure 2. Frequency of neurological deficits in patients with MFPS by occupational group

Furthermore, three main types of disorders are considered: sensory disorders, muscle weakness, and autonomic symptoms (Fig. 2). They were most common among production workers (32.7%), which is associated with intense physical exertion, repetitive movements and exposure to vibration, leading to irritation of the nerve endings. Sensory disorders were recorded in 25.0% of medical personnel and 18.5% of office employees, which may be associated with the predominantly static nature of the workload and prolonged holding of the neck in a fixed position. Manufacturing employees also had the highest percentage of muscle weakness (25.5%), reflecting the impact of physical overload and muscle fatigue. Muscle weakness was found in 16.7% of medical staff and 12.3% of office workers, indicating a lighter workload and predominantly functional rather than structural muscle damage.

They are most pronounced among production workers (16.4%), which may be due to a combination of physical and psycho-emotional stress. Among medical staff, vegetative disorders were found in 13.3%, and among office workers less frequently (7.7%), which reflects a lower degree of stress and static tension in their professional activities.

Neurological deficits in patients with MFPS depend on the nature of their occupational stress. Manufacturing employees demonstrate the most pronounced sensory and motor impairments, as well as vegetative manifestations. Office employees and medical staff experience neurological disorders less frequently, and these are moderate in nature. These data emphasise the need for professionally oriented diagnostics and an individual approach to the treatment of MFPS, taking into account the specifics of the work and the load on the cervical-brachial region.

Thus, the results confirm the need for a professionally oriented approach to the diagnosis and treatment of MFPS, including: ergonomic correction, physical rehabilitation, work with trigger points, as well as psychocorrection and training in methods of self-control of load. This approach not only reduces the intensity of pain syndrome, but also reduces the frequency of relapses, improves the functional state of the cervical spine, and preserves the working capacity of patients.

Conclusions. The structure of clinical forms of myofascial pain syndrome in patients from different occupational groups shows marked differences. Trigger points are most often located on the back of the neck and in the upper part of the trapezius muscle, while the subscapular region is more commonly affected in manufacturing employees and medical staff. The bilateral nature of the process prevails in all groups, and the combination with cervicalgia and cervicobrachialgia is most pronounced in manufacturing employees, which is associated with high physical exertion and repetitive movements. Neurological deficits, including sensory disturbances, muscle weakness, and autonomic symptoms, are more common in manufacturing employees and less common in office employees, while medical personnel demonstrate intermediate rates. These data confirm the link between neurological symptoms and the nature of occupational stress and serve as a valuable tool for the differential diagnosis of MFBS and radiculopathy. The multifactorial pathogenesis of MFPS combines mechanical stress and neurological disorders, with the severity of each component depending on the occupational group, which requires a differentiated approach to diagnosis and treatment. The practical significance lies in the need for professionally oriented comprehensive rehabilitation, including correction of workplace ergonomics, trigger point therapy, physical rehabilitation, and training in methods of self-control of muscle tension. This approach helps to reduce the intensity of pain, decrease the frequency of relapses, and maintain patients' ability to work.

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